

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən praktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
17-18 sentyabr 2024, Naxçıvan Azərbaycan**

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DRIVER OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTIONS IS THE STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT. The article analyzes the dates, goals and tasks of the Industrial revolutions, examines their main attributes and evaluates the role of artificial intelligence in their development. It is shown that starting from the 3rd industrial revolution, artificial intelligence plays the role of the leading technology of the next revolutions, and other advanced technologies serve its development. Therefore, the main research directions and prospects of development of artificial intelligence are investigated. 3 main types of artificial intelligence are compared and their development prospects are considered. Examples of scientific research works performed at SSU in the direction of application of artificial intelligence technologies are considered.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, industrial revolution, autonomous robots, Internet of Things, computer modeling.

XÜLASƏ. Məruzə tezisində Sənaye inqilablarının yaranma tarixləri, məqsədləri və vəzifələri analiz olunur, onların əsas atributları araşdırılır və inkişafında süni intellektin rolu qiymətləndirilir. Göstərilir ki, 3-cü sənaye inqilabından başlayaraq süni intellekt növbəti inqilabların aparıcı texnologiyası rolunu oynayır və digər mütərəqqi texnologiyalar onun inkişafına xidmət edirlər. Odur ki, süni intellektin əsas tədqiqat istiqamətləri və inkişafının perspektivləri araşdırılır. Süni intellektin 3 əsas növü müqayisəli analiz edilir və inkişafı perspektivlərinə baxılır. Süni intellekt texnologiyalarının tətbiqi istiqamətində SDU-da yerinə yetirilən elmi-tədqiqat işlərinin nümunələrinə baxılır.

Açar sözlər: süni intellekt, sənaye inqilabı, avtonom robotlar, əşya interneti, kompüter modelləşdirilməsi.

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Introduction. In all eras, people regularly made new searches in the direction of increasing and at the same time easing their physical and mental functions in their activities and achieved certain results. It should also be noted that each of the achievements in the indicated directions created an incentive for the further development of the other and they complemented each other in their interaction. The scientific, organizational and practical works carried out in this direction have been formed and studied in history as industrial revolutions. Currently, world science and industry is on the verge of the IV industrial revolution.

Before explaining the main tasks and perspectives of the IV industrial revolution, let's make a short excursion to the industrial revolutions that have developed and differed by certain achievements.

1. **Development history, goals and tasks of industrial revolutions.** 1st Industrial revolution (late 18th century), transition from manual labor to machine tools. Key attributes of the 1st industrial revolution: the mechanical sewing machine and steam engines. It is natural that these labor tools, along with increasing the physical abilities and functions of people, also played a positive role in the creation of innovations and habits in their mental activities.

2nd Industrial revolution (late 19th century to mid 20th century). Main attributes: conveyor manufacturing, power plants, incandescent light bulbs, electronic lamps, telephone, electronic calculators, etc.

3rd Industrial revolution (from the middle of the 20th century). Main attributes: transistor integrated circuits, processor, microprocessor, computer, internet, digital camera, logic controller, etc. The 3rd industrial revolution began in 1960. Conventionally, the first programmable logic controllers, high-performance computers and industrial robots are considered as the beginning.

The main feature of the indicated industrial revolutions is that all three of them serve to improve any new device, type of production, computing elements, and most importantly, the mental and physical abilities of people.

The 4th Industrial revolution (Komissarov, 2015) differs from the 3rd in two main ways: the differences between the numerical, physical and biological worlds disappear; technologies change very fast.

The main difference of the 4th Industrial revolution from the previous ones is that to get any information about it, not keywords and the term key technologies that will come out of scientific works and experiments in the near future will be used. The following can be attributed to those key technologies:

1. Big data analytics
2. Artificial intelligence
3. **Autonomous robots**
4. **Autonomous transport and drones**
5. **Cloud computing**
6. Quantum calculations
7. **Internet of Things (IoT)**
8. Virtual reality
9. **Computer modeling and simulators**
10. Three-dimensional printing
11. Printed electronics
12. Nano and neurotechnologies
13. **Information security**

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14. *Cybersecurity*

Already in some areas in the materials of the International Economic Forum held in 2019 the beginning of the revolution is reflected (in italics in the list).

It is shown that the started 4th Industrial revolution is already achieving satisfactory results, especially in the directions of points 3, 4, 7, 9. Among them, Internet of Things technology is of particular importance.

The Internet of Things is a network concept that provides data transfer and use in interaction between intelligent physical objects (things). Examples of IoT devices include: smart mobile phones, refrigerators, watches, fire alarms, medical transmitters, security systems, etc.

The term Internet of Things refers to a collective network in which devices and technologies connected to it can freely and easily interact with each other.

Analysts of the Chisko company believe that the Internet of Things was born in 2008 and 2009. So, in that period, the number of devices and technologies connected to the global network exceeded the number of the population of the earth, and thus the transition from “Human Internet” to Internet of Things took place.

The following main results can be shown when comparing the dates of creation, tasks and achievements of industrial revolutions.

1. All industrial revolutions occurred as a result of historical necessity and are related to the following factors: the emergence and development of new production areas (textile industry, metallurgy, steam engines); industrialization, i.e. transition from agrarian economy to industrial production (engineering, transport, communications, chemistry, etc.); social changes (innovations in social structures, education).

2. The main goal of any industrial revolution is to serve to change people's lifestyle for the better and to develop and implement approaches to improve their mental and physical activities.

3. All Industrial revolutions involve machine imitations of human creative functions using at least some elements of artificial intelligence. Therefore, artificial intelligence technologies can be considered the locomotive of Industrial revolutions. Especially since the 3rd Industrial Revolution, Artificial Intelligence plays the role of the leading technology of the next revolutions, and other progressive technologies serve its development.

Taking into account the above, the research directions of artificial intelligence are considered in the thesis of the report.

2. *Main research directions and prospects of development of artificial intelligence.* Artificial intelligence as a field of science began to be formed in the stage of rapid development of computer techniques and technologies starting from the middle of the 20th century. In the territory of the former USSR, in 1974, under the leadership of academician G.S. Pospelov and professor D.A. Pospelov, a department on artificial intelligence problems was established under the EA of the USSR. As a result of

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Picture. The classic structure of the main research directions of artificial intelligence

the activity of this department, two international conferences on artificial intelligence were held in Tbilisi and Repino in 1975 and 1977. World-class artificial intelligence scientists participated in these forums: I. McCarthy, M. Arbib, L. Zadeh, D. Denat, D. Miki, I. Moore, Nilson, P. 8inston, K. Huinrt, E. Fredkin, E. Sandeval, K. Simon and others. In such an authoritative forum, the current situation, achievements and perspectives of artificial intelligence problems were examined and a road map of scientific research works to be performed in this field was developed.

A brief summary of the works performed in the past period in the direction indicated in the thesis of the report is reviewed, the results achieved and development prospects are examined.

The picture shows the classic structure of the main research directions of Artificial Intelligence (Pospelov, 1988, p.280, Ahmadov , 2015 ,98).

Direction A began to be studied before other directions of artificial intelligence and mainly involves the solving of problems such as the automatic synthesis of software modules of creative functions unique to humans, especially game problems (chess, checkers, dominoes, etc.), the analysis and synthesis of musical works.

It is from this point of view that the term Artificial Intelligence was born. The main goal of this direction was the creation of devices (physical models) capable of simulating various functions of humans and other living beings by using the existing achievements of science and technology at that time. Although certain achievements were made in this direction, especially in the field of the army (night vision devices, reading and processing of images, etc.), the rapid development of computer techniques and technologies, the emergence of new algorithmic, software, technical support, the idea that the direction A of artificial intelligence is not the only one actualized.

It is necessary to note the special role of the intellectual interface in its classical structure in the development of B and C research directions of artificial intelligence. The Intelligent interface, which includes the most positive features of early, terminal intervention and new information processing technologies at the stages of development of computer equipment and technologies, allows various professions to communicate with Artificial Intelligence technologies in their own professional languages and use its achievements. For this purpose, intelligent systems developed over a long period of time - information search, application package programs, arithmetic-logic software packages, experts, etc., are included in the intellectual interface.

One of the most relevant directions of artificial intelligence in the modern era is the creation of algorithmic, software and technical support of intelligent robots that provide purposeful behavior in conditions of uncertainty, adapt to situations occurring in internal and external environments, and achieve the set goal. Direction D of artificial intelligence technology deals with solving the problems of performing scientific and research works in the direction of solving the indicated issues.

The main issue in the direction of improving the classical structure of the research directions of artificial intelligence is to enrich its intellectual interface with modern intellectual systems and with modern, especially Soft Computing technologies. (fuzzy logic, Neural networks, learning theory, genetic algorithms, etc.).

Based on the analysis of the history and achievements of the emergence and development of industrial revolutions, as well as the study of the research directions of Artificial Intelligence technology, it can be shown that in all cases and in the expected next industrial revolutions, Artificial Intelligence

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technologies play a leading role as the main research direction and will not lose their relevance in the future.

Therefore, the history, types, achievements and perspectives of the development of artificial intelligence technologies are considered in the thesis of the report.

3. Three main types of artificial intelligence. According to Alan Turing: Artificial intelligence is the scientific and technical technologies that create intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs.

In the field of data processing in various spheres, the algorithms of Artificial Intelligence already exceed human computing ability a million times. Those algorithms are already able to perform some “creative” functions of a person. However, some unsolved problems, especially ethical ones, still exist.

Machine learning systems, which are already considered the main subsystem of Artificial Intelligence, have automated processes in all vital fields (banking, medicine, security, industry, etc.).

They distinguish 3 main types of artificial intelligence: weak, simple (A1); strong, general (AG1) and collective, super (super AG1).

In all periods of industrial revolutions, type A1 was almost simply and partially fully realized. There are many examples that are of particular importance today and simulate human creative functions with devices and computers, including: industrial and intelligent robots for various purposes; advertisements on social networks; facial recognition, voice assistants, etc.

The AG1 type is an artificial intelligence that is maximally approximated to the capabilities of human intelligence and is based on the principle of self-awareness and the ability to generalize according to Turing's classical definition.

According to experts, AG1 can be formed by about 2075, and after about 30 years, the formation of super Artificial Intelligence is predicted.

Super AI is not just about being similar to human intelligence, but surpassing the intellectual abilities of the smartest in all fields. So the Super AI must improve by reprogramming itself and freely run new algorithms and systems.

Summarizing the results of the analysis of the types of artificial intelligence, the following can be shown:

1. Artificial intelligence is the imitation of human natural intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems.

2. Artificial intelligence is represented by the following main specific applied systems: expert, natural language information processing, speech and machine vision recognition, etc.

3. Currently, the Google Translate program has the ability to translate large blocks of characters. Neural networks perform context-aware operations on statistical data represented by large arrays. It is now possible to read and understand articles written in those languages without knowing Indian, Chinese and Arabic languages. With the help of artificial intelligence algorithms, doctors can diagnose various diseases. Algorithms based on flexible neural networks are capable of generating articles on any topic, etc.

At the end of the article, we would like to give brief information about the scientific research works carried out at SSU.

Starting from the 80s of the last century, at SSU (the Sumgayit branch of the former Azerbaijan Oil and Chemical Institute), the purpose of designing robotic complexes using modern automation tools (Industrial robots and other mechatronic devices) that were particularly relevant for that period and applying them in industrial enterprises of Sumgayit city scientific-research works began to be carried out

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with First of all, the production of Evaporators of the Sumgayit aluminum plant was chosen as the research object. Under the leadership of Professor R. A. Aliyev, a working group was created, which was made up of employees and scientists of various designated departments of the institute. Already in 1984, for the first time in the South Caucasus, a robotic complex that creates a package from aluminum sheets and rolls it on a rolling machine was designed and applied in the active production in the South Caucasus.

In order to ensure the real-time operation of the robotic complex, algorithms based on the production rules of artificial intelligence were developed and applied using the principle of situational control in its computer control system.

The results of the scientific-research works carried out in the indicated direction were continued with the design and application of robotic complexes in other areas of the production of vaporizers.

At the same time, in other industrial enterprises of Sumgayit, the compressor plant, Pipe-rolling, etc., the aforementioned complexes were designed and implemented.

It is worth noting that the results of the conducted scientific-research works were summarized and 14 candidacy and 6 doctoral theses were defended and appropriate scientific degrees were obtained, and the vast majority of those scientists are currently working at SSU.

Although the activity in the direction of application was stopped due to the well-known events of the 1990s, the theoretical scientific-research works are successfully continued today in the Faculty of Engineering. Thus, the scientists of the faculty use advanced technologies of artificial intelligence (Soft Computing) and computer modeling devices (Petri net, production rules, Frame and logic models, etc.) in accordance with the requirements of the modern era in the direction of situational management of flexible production systems (research direction D of artificial intelligence on) continue their scientific research work (Ahmadov , 2015 ,p.98, Ахмедов, 2023,с. 218). The application of the results of the carried out scientific-research works in the educational process is of particular importance.

At the same time, scientific-research works are being successfully continued at SSU in the B direction of Artificial Intelligence (external intelligence of the computer), especially in the field of creating automated design systems and increasing their intelligence using modern technologies (Гусейнов, 2022,с. 35, Hyseynov, 2016, p.20, Mammadov, 2022, p.85).

Literature

1. Komissarov, A. The fourth industrial revolution. Vedomosti, No. 3938 (October 14, 2015).
2. Искусственный интеллект - основа новой информационной технологии / Pospelov G.S.-M.: Nauka, 1988. - 280 p. Ил.- я (ber. Academic reading).
3. Ahmadov M.A., Mahammadli H.M. Methods of automated modeling and research of information systems. Baku: Azeri, 2015.
4. Ахмедов М.А., Насирова Э.А. Инструмент автоматизированного проектирования компьютерной модели ГПМ и ее комплексное исследование компьютерными экспериментами. Труды Международного наугно-технигеского конгресеа <<Интеллектуальные системы и информационные технолог -2023 >>. ИС & ИТ-2023 >>. Таганрог 2023. Стр. 218-223
5. Гусейнов А. Г., Салимова М.Р. Агентно- ориентированный подход к просктированию гибких производственных систем // Вестник Астраханского государственного технического университета. Серия : Управление, вычислительная техника и информатика. 2022. № 4. С. 35-41.

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6. Huseynov A.H. Agent technology at computing option of flexible manufacture system element and composed structure // Advanced Mathematical Models and Applications. 2016 .V. 1.N.1.P. 20-27.

7. Mammadov C.F., Huseynov A.H., Hasanova Y.M., Salimova M.R.. Algorithmic and mathematical support for topology research of the corporative networks// Advanced mathematical models & applications. 2022. V.7.N.1. P. 85-92

**ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ ДВИЖУЩЕЙ СИЛОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ РЕВОЛЮЦИЙ**

Ахмедов М.А., Гусейнов А.Х., Ахмедова С.М.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, промышленная революция, автономные роботы, Интернет вещей, компьютерное моделирование.

В тезисе доклада анализируются история, цели и задачи промышленных революций, исследуются их основные атрибуты и оценивается роль искусственного интеллекта в их развитии. Показано, что начиная с Третьей промышленной революции искусственный интеллект играет роль ведущей технологии последующих революций, а другие прогрессивные технологии служат его развитию. Поэтому рассмотрены основные направления исследований и перспективы развития искусственного интеллекта. Сравниваются 3 основных типа искусственного интеллекта и рассматриваются перспективы их развития.

Рассмотрены примеры научно-исследовательских работ, выполняемых в СумГУ в направлении применения технологий искусственного интеллекта.

**SÜNI İNTELLEKT SƏNAYE İNQILABLARININ İNKİŞAFININ HƏRƏKƏTVERİCİ
QÜVVƏSİDİR**

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Açar sözlər: süni intellekt, sənaye inqilabı, avtonom robotlar, əşya interneti, kompüter modelləşdirilməsi.

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